

Factors Affecting the Success of Agile Software Development Projects in Sri Lanka

Y.M.D. Yapa¹

*Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka*

¹dilushayap99@gmail.com, ²malkanathi@sjp.ac.lk

Abstract

Project success in Agile software development is influenced by several critical factors. This study aims to identify the factors that impact Agile software development success by focusing on people, organizational, and technical factors. The study examined how team skills and collaboration, organizational support and culture, and the use of effective tools and practices contribute to project success. This study followed a quantitative approach to answer the research questions. The convenience sampling method was used to select the sample for the study. Data was gathered by circulating an online survey questionnaire among IT Project Managers. Data was analyzed using advanced multivariate statistical software of Structural Equation Modelling (SmartPLS). The findings of the study provided considerable support for hypothesized relationships. The study findings revealed that personal characteristics have the most significant effect on Agile software development project success. This study provided some important implications for software development companies, project managers, and other relevant authorities on measures that could be taken used to ensure the success of Agile software projects. For organizations, understanding the critical success factors in Agile projects can lead to more effective strategy formulation, resource allocation, and process improvement. Project managers can apply these findings to overcome the complexities of Agile software development, optimize team performance, and enhance project delivery. The cross-sectional design hindered past behavior examinations, suggesting a longitudinal design for future studies. Future studies are also encouraged to consider combining quantitative and qualitative methods. Furthermore, it contributed to reducing the gap in the body of knowledge regarding factors affecting Agile Software Project Success in the Sri Lankan context.

Keywords: *Agile Software Development, Organization Factors, Technical Factors, People Factors*